

GENERATIVE EFFICIENCY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HISTORICAL WORLDVIEW OF ACADEMIC LYCEUM STUDENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18399233>

Abstract. *This article presents and analyzes scholars' scientific views on historical knowledge, levels of understanding the past in the development of historical worldview, methodological approaches to historical thinking based on these, the generative nature of historical knowledge, and the enhancement of skills.*

Keywords: *Integrative model, differential connections, historical worldview, historical event, integrativity, historical consciousness, historical thinking, evolutionary process, self-awareness, self-development, historical concepts, public reception offices, virtual reception offices.*

INTRODUCTION

When teaching history, the primary focus is on encouraging students to study factual data in this discipline, reflect on it, and express their attitudes, as well as ensuring the generative nature of learning tasks on the subject, which contributes to the formation of a historical worldview about the past. Along with this, the work of academic lyceum students with historical facts and information plays a crucial role in developing their historical perspective. Special attention is given to the historical worldview, drawing on the content of research by specialists in this field. In this regard, enhancing academic lyceum students' knowledge about the conceptual foundation of the distinctive structural semantics of worldview, historical worldview, historical thinking, and consciousness leads to increased effectiveness in learning.

METHODS. According to E. Yu. Semenova, "The study of worldviews, social attitudes, and behavioral practices is of great importance for determining the foundations of everyday life, since everyday life shapes worldviews and social attitudes, reflecting their components in the manifestations of life activities" [1]. P. C. Seixas notes: "If history is truly a way of knowing the world, then through it we transform past events into a form meaningful to us in the present. In this process, students understand history as a process of acquiring knowledge, engaging in the mastery of primary and secondary information about the past" [2].

"A worldview consists of one's attitude towards the surrounding world and existence, general ideas about the principles and foundations of life, the philosophy of human life, and the entire body of knowledge about it. Indeed, a person assimilates certain experiences through a scientific approach to life and observation, applies this knowledge, and becomes accustomed to repeating methods that have proven effective. In this sense, a worldview can be considered not as a logical system of a particular level, but as a product of a person's belief in existence and values" [3].

"In society, special importance is attached to individual freedom. This contributes to the rapid enrichment of young people's worldview, which is developing ever more dynamically. The field of struggle for enriching and purposefully shaping worldviews is gradually transforming into

a significant ideological arena. Therefore, actively influencing the worldview of young people and educating them in the spirit of devotion to our ancestors and historical heritage remains an important task”[1]. As M.M. Cochrane notes, ”If a historical worldview is combined with primary and secondary knowledge about the past, then primary and secondary knowledge depend on historical thinking. Historical arguments based on facts about the past are interpreted as concrete facts or concepts”[1].

According to R. Ashby, P. Lee, and D. Shemilt, "students who perceive history as an activity based on the interpretation of facts can learn to use evidence as the foundation for their thinking”[1]. There is a distinction between historical worldview and historical thinking, and they are considered as separately defined concepts. “According to M.S. Kagan, the universality of a worldview lies in the fact that it incorporates an individual component and is characterized by the use of both inductive and deductive reasoning”[2]. According to Singer-Gabella, "effectively utilizing historical literature to adapt the expressed characteristics of generativity for the purpose of identifying generative tasks in history”[3].

RESULTS. The set of factors for generative tasks in the development of historical worldview includes:

- Forming conclusions based on historical sources and contextual data, developing a new historical worldview in students through historical reasoning that builds upon their previously acquired knowledge.

- Encouraging students to express their attitudes towards historical and factual perspectives by defining and memorizing their historical existence;

Joint analysis of productive ideas from works related to historical figures in the educational process, fostering students' creative abilities.

Consequently, the criteria for assessing contextualized functions in the model for developing the historical worldview of academic lyceum students in the context of New Uzbekistan are related to the deconstruction of the subject-subject structure and the interactive work between students and teachers.

The proportional approach to mentality in the development of historical worldview is characterized by the harmony between spiritual life and societal progress, and the alignment of social consciousness with social being.

“Literature on historical worldview confirms that for the development of historical knowledge, it is crucial to understand central concepts (such as facts) and to become familiar with the methods historians use to investigate and interpret the past. This is achieved through studying a range of historical, scientific, and philosophical texts in the field of history” [5].

As part of our research, we have developed the evolution of historical worldview as a holistic structure based on methodological principles. The information in the textbook on historical worldview, the study of our ancestors' heritage, and the analysis of works and images created by creative figures allow for an in-depth examination of students' personal attitudes towards the reality under consideration and their independent analysis.

DISCUSSION. The paradigm of comparative-historical analysis - historical events - historical figures, historical facts: based on this triad, differences and similarities in content are compared and contrasted during the learning process in interaction with the student.

According to O.S. Porshneva, ”the methodological approach is fundamental in the study of mentality and historical worldview. Following the civilizational approach, researchers have viewed mentality as a subconscious part of the human psyche, separating it from social

consciousness and studying it in this capacity” [6]. According to M.S. Kagan, "Others, while studying historical processes related to the spiritual life of society, established the dependence of social consciousness on social existence” [7]

The theory and methodology of teaching history develop differentiated approaches in students of academic lyceums, guiding them towards understanding and comprehension of historical reality. "Recognition of the pattern and necessity of transitioning from the empirical level of understanding the historical process to the theoretical level of its comprehension and explanation." Methodological principles serve as methodological guidelines, especially when studying multifaceted problems [3]”.

“Studying medieval society's understanding of historical reality, J. Le Goff emphasized that it reflects the unity of the material conditions in which members of this society live and the world of their perceptions” [6]. “A.Ya. Gurevich, applying a historical-anthropological approach, reanalyzed the ideas of medieval society and presented his comprehensive conclusions and solutions through the prism of his own reflections” [7]. “The combination of historical personality and historicity, along with the efficacy of scientific objectivity and systematic approach, represents an interpretation of the general problems of history as an amalgamation of worldview and its traditional philosophical components” [8].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the development of a historical worldview in students of academic lyceums is a valuable component that serves to advance their axiological, ontological, and cognitive approaches. At the same time, by examining the lives of historical figures, students cultivate a range of abilities, such as the capacity to emulate role models, reflect human qualities in relation

to historical realities, engage in self-development, and practice self-management - all of which manifest as intellectual growth.

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